

Massive black holes

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Abstract

This study explores the core structure of massive black holes that originate from supernovae. Introducing the concept of "Dachus density," a state of maximum matter density. It results from combining the fundamental physics principles of "Uniformity of Physics Laws in the Universe Principle" and the "Energy Conservation Principle." Together, they impose that the total Energy in the Universe is fixed, meaning there is no place in space-time with infinite Energy. Therefore, an upper limit exists for Matter density. I propose that this density characterizes the core of all massive black holes. Through examining Cygnus X-1 and Sagittarius A*, I calculate core dimensions and event horizon sizes, revealing that a black hole's core volume is up to ~150 orders of magnitude smaller than its event horizon volume in Sagittarius A*. This state suggests a core-mantle structure, where the "mantle" lies between the core and the event horizon. Additionally, I discuss the effects of a rotating Dachus core on this structure and propose two methods to check whether massive black holes universally exhibit this compact core with a surrounding mantle.

Article

1. Motivation

In recent years, the study of supermassive black holes has revolutionized our understanding of galaxies' structures. Despite significant advances in observational astronomy and theoretical modeling, the fundamental question remains: What is the structure of massive black holes? Addressing this question is important for advancing our knowledge of the Universe.

New and future astrophysical observations will help determine the structure of massive black holes.

Throughout this article, when referring to Matter, Energy also applies.

2. Massive black hole structure and event horizons sizes

Massive Black Hole Definition:

A massive black hole is a black hole with a single core resulting from a supernova event.

From observations, the Mass of massive black holes is usually $> \sim 8M_{\odot}$. (1)

Combining the "Uniformity of Physics Laws in the Universe Principle": **Each physics law is the same throughout the Cosmos,**" and the Energy Conservation Principle: "**Energy in a closed system is conserved and finite,**" results in the conclusion that the total amount of Energy in the Cosmos is fixed. **Note:** There is no known instance, whether on Earth, within our solar system, or in distant galaxies, where the above principles have been invalidated.

The only way to guarantee it is if and only if there is no possibility of infinite Energy density even at a space-time point. This condition means there is no place in the Universe with infinite Matter density. This restriction leads us to conclude that a state of Matter with a maximum density MUST exist.

I called this state of maximum Matter density "**Dachus**" (derived from the Hebrew word for compressed.) I denoted Dachus density by ρ_D .

Inside a black hole, the continual compression of Matter compresses the Matter until it reaches Dachus density within a non-zero volume in the center of the black hole. Any further compression only contributes to the expansion of the black hole's core size, which maintains its Dachus state.

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Discussion: The idea of a black hole without a singularity poses a significant challenge to well-established theoretical models, which assert that singularities are inevitable at the heart of such objects. These predictions, rooted in the equations of general relativity, have been formulated by prominent physicists. However, it is essential to recognize that these models did not consider the possibility of a maximum limit on Matter density. This new knowledge negates their conclusion's validity that all geodesics within a black hole must converge at a singularity. As a result, the interior structure of black holes differs fundamentally from a singularity-based structure.

During the supernova contraction phase, the gravitational attraction force is so significant that it overcomes the tremendous deflecting centrifugal force of the spinning elementary particles, and the repulsion forces of electric charges with the same electric sign and creates a massive black hole with a small core at its center in Dachus density. In this core, all Energy compresses to the Dachus state. The elementary particles stop spinning individually because, in the Dachus state, there is no room for movement (the constituents of the black hole's core do not move in relation to each other).

A question arises: We know from observations that black holes spin, so their cores must spin. Thus, how does the core of a black hole continue to spin if all its kinetic Energy has been compressed out? The answer lies in the nature of uncertainty-related Energy. This form of Energy is purely kinetic. It continually appears and disappears throughout space-time, including within the core of massive black holes. As pure kinetic Energy, uncertainty-related Energy replenishes the kinetic Energy necessary to sustain the spin of the black hole's core. **Note:** This uncertainty-related Energy cannot remain within the core due to its Dachus state, and thus quickly exits the core - and new uncertainty-related Energy appears.

After creating the massive black hole, the mighty gravitational attraction forces keep bending the space-time curvature around the core, causing Energy near the core to join the core and then compressing it up to the Dachus density. (This is how a massive black hole's core grows.)

The region from the core boundary to the black hole's outer boundary (the black hole's event horizon) will be known as the "**Black Hole Mantle.**"

Aside: Are there circumstances where a black hole and its core shrink?

Discussion: There are two possibilities: When anti-Matter encounters its corresponding Matter at the core's rim, they annihilate each other, and some of the Matter charges may spread outside the core because of the kinetic Energy discharged. On very rare occasions, a surge of very intense uncertainty-related Energy hits the core's rim, and if it is intense enough, it tears away some charges from the core's rim. Both these occurrences can reduce the core size.

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The occurrences mentioned above also apply to the black hole's mantle and horizon. If these events occur at the black hole's horizon, its size will decrease.

How big are the cores and horizons of spinning massive black holes?

The quarkic (aka color) charge does not affect massive black holes at their event horizons because the quarkic charge diminishing point (range) is much less than the massive black holes' event horizons. Negative and positive electric charges appear in equal quantities and negate each other, so they do not influence the event horizon of the massive black hole.

Therefore, I will use the Kerr equation to calculate the massive black hole's event horizon:

$R_{Black\ hole}^2 - \frac{2 \cdot M \cdot G \cdot R_{Black\ hole}}{c^2} + a^2 = 0$, where $R_{Black\ hole}$ is the massive black hole event horizon radius and $M = M_{Black\ hole}$ (throughout this article.)

Because of the mighty attraction forces within the massive black hole, I can assume that (almost) all the black hole Mass resides in its very small core (see calculations below.) Thus, I can treat the Mass of a massive black hole as a point Mass in the following angular momentum calculations.

$$J = MvR_{Black\ hole}, \quad a = \frac{J}{Mc} = \frac{v}{c}R_{Black\ hole}, \quad (2)$$

Remark: The observed Mass "M" already includes the relativistic effects.

Equation 1 Event horizon radius for a rotating massive black hole with a core at Dachus density

$$R_{Black\ hole} = \frac{2MG}{c^2 + v^2}$$

Where "v" is the linear velocity at the equator of the spinning black hole.

Note: The calculations presented here assume a spherical shape for the massive black hole and its core. I have not considered their slight flattening at their poles near the spin axis, which occurs when they spin very fast.

I will calculate the Dachus core radius using:

Equation 2 Dachus core radius

$$r_D = \left(\frac{3M_{Blackhole}}{4\pi\rho_D} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

I will use two examples. The first is a massive black hole named Cygnus X-1 in the Cygnus constellation. It has 21.2 ± 2.2 Solar Masses. (3) The second is a supermassive black hole in the

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center of the Milky Way galaxy named Sagittarius A* with $4.154 \mp 0.014 \cdot 10^6$ solar Masses. (4)

Discussion: Massive black stars retain some of the angular momentum from their progenitor stars, which, in turn, inherited angular momentum from the rotating dust clouds that preceded their formation. Consequently, because black holes are significantly smaller than their progenitor stars - the angular momentum conservation implies that they should rotate extremely fast:

To calculate the spinning velocity of massive black holes, I use their *dimensionless* α .

Some observations show that for Cygnus X-1: $\alpha \approx 0.967$ (3σ). (5) Other observations suggest that the value is higher: $\alpha > 0.9985$ (3σ) (6) In the calculation, I will use the approximation value of $v \sim 0.967c$. (See the calculations for the " α " in the next chapter.)

Observations show that for Sagittarius A*: *dimensionless* $\alpha \approx 0.90 \pm 0.06$. (7) In the calculation, I will use $v \sim 0.90c$.

In the calculations I used $\rho_D \approx 7.139538044 \cdot 10^{156} [Kg m^{-3}]$ - this value is a result of calculations on extremely small, spinning black holes. (8)

Table 1 Sizes comparison for Dachus core versus the entire black hole event horizon for highly relativistically rotating massive black holes

Star	Solar Masses	Dachus core (r_D)	
		Radius [m]	Volume [m ³]
Cygnus X-1	21.2 ± 2.2	$1.1212 \cdot 10^{-42}$	$5.9031 \cdot 10^{-126}$
Sagittarius A*	$4.154 \pm 0.014 \cdot 10^6$	$6.5119 \cdot 10^{-41}$	$1.1567 \cdot 10^{-120}$

Star	Event horizon ($R_{Black\ hole}$)	
	Radius [Km]	Volume [Km ³]
Cygnus X-1	32.3	$1.42 \cdot 10^5$
Sagittarius A*	6,776,393	$1.30 \cdot 10^{21}$

The massive black hole's core is a speck compared to its total size. Cygnus X-1's Dachus core volume is approximately $4 \cdot 10^{-140}$ of its event horizon volume, and Sagittarius A*'s Dachus core volume is approximately $9 \cdot 10^{-151}$ of its event horizon volume.

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Our understanding of the Energy density distribution within a massive black hole remains limited regarding the black hole's mantle. The mantle likely revolves at high speeds due to its creation method and the relativistic rotation of the Dachus core, which drags its surrounding Energy, causing mantle rotation and turbulence.

Note: Given that the cores are minuscule relative to the overall size of black holes, it is unsurprising that singularity-based black hole calculations have appeared accurate. However, a core in the Dachus state aligns with the most fundamental laws of physics, particularly the 'Uniformity of Physical Laws in the Universe Principle,' unlike a singularity, which violates them.

3. Two method to determine whether massive black holes have an internal structure

Question: How can we know that a massive black hole has an internal structure (a core and mantle structure and not a single solid structure)?

Note: A massive black hole with a single solid structure is one whose core is the entire black hole, for example.

3.1. First method – Measuring the radius of the black hole:

For a structureless black hole - a solid sphere revolving relativistically fast:

$$J = \frac{3}{4} M v r_{Black\ hole} \quad (9) \quad \text{under the limit } \omega r < c. \quad a = \frac{J}{MC}.$$

Equation 3 Event horizon radius for a solid rotating massive black hole (without a core)

$$R_{Black\ hole} = \frac{2MG}{c^2 + \frac{9}{16} v^2}$$

Table 2 Calculations of black hole event horizon radius with and without a structure

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Black hole	Cygnus X-1	Sagittarius A*	M87*
Solar Masses	$21.2 \pm 2.2 \odot$	$4.154 \pm 0.014 \cdot 10^6 \odot$	$6.5 \pm 0.9 \cdot 10^9 \odot$
Revolution speed at the equator	$0.967c [m s^{-1}]$	$0.9c [m s^{-1}]$	$0.94c [m s^{-1}]$
Radius for a structure of core and mantle	$3.235 \cdot 10^4 [m]$	$6.776 \cdot 10^9 [m]$	$1.019 \cdot 10^{13} [m]$
Radius for a solid sphere (no structure.)	$4.102 \cdot 10^4 [m]$	$8.426 \cdot 10^9 [m]$	$1.282 \cdot 10^{13} [m]$

If observation abides by the predictions above, we will know that massive black holes have a core at Dachus state and a mantle. The existing published measurements are not accurate enough to distinguish between the two possibilities. However, most, if not all, scientists agree that most of the massive black hole Mass is at its center.

3.2. Second method – Measuring the α of the black hole:

Using $\alpha = \frac{a \cdot c^2}{G \cdot M} = \frac{v \cdot r \cdot c}{G \cdot M}$ [dimensionless], then substituting the solution for $R_{Black\ hole}$ of the Kerr solution in this equation yields a quadratic equation: $\alpha \cdot v^2 - 2c \cdot v + \alpha \cdot c^2 = 0$, so $v = \frac{c \pm \sqrt{c^2 - \alpha^2 c^2}}{\alpha}$. For Cygnus X-1 if $v = 0.967c$, then α should be 0.99944. A recent study suggested that $\alpha > 0.9985 (3\sigma)$, which corresponds pretty accurately to the choice of spinning velocity and the core-mantle structure of massive black holes. (6)

4. Importance of astrophysical observations in determining the existence of black holes' Dachus core

Every black hole created in a supernova has a core at Dachus state. However, the smallest ones (quantum black holes) are too small to observe with current instruments.

Only Massive and supermassive black holes are big enough to supply evidence of a Dachus core's existence inside them. An internal structure of a core in a non-zero volume will have a minute influence on the black hole mantle behavior and, therefore, on the event horizon behavior and the volume outside the black hole event horizon. (10) (11)

5. 0[K]?

Temperature is a measure of the movement of particles and their subatomic constituents.

What happens if there is no particle movement?

To answer, I need to use a known limit:

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Minimal Temperature Limit Definition:

The minimal temperature limit is "Absolute Zero," designated as 0[K], which corresponds to the complete absence of kinetic Energy in a system.

The complete absence of kinetic Energy is equivalent to “no particle movement.”

Note: absolute zero (0[K]) seems impossible with the existence of uncertainty-related Energy:
(12)

Question: Is there a place in space-time where the temperature is 0[K]?

Discussion: The Matter within a black hole's core is always at the Dachus state. It remains motionless when comparing subparts of the core to other subparts of the core. (Any movement within the core's subparts would indicate additional space for compression – which is impossible in this Dachus state.)

I have discussed that uncertainty-related Energy always appears and disappears everywhere. Therefore, there are always bursts of kinetic Energy in every black hole's core for an extremely short time, which appears as rotational Energy.

Note: The uncertainty-related Energy within the core exits swiftly, but new uncertainty-related Energy always appears again within the core.

From observations, massive black holes spin and move through space-time; therefore, their temperature is higher than absolute zero (within their cores and mantle.)

Suppose a massive black hole's core that does not move exists, notably, does not spin; then and only then is its core at a standstill. In this state, none of its composing components move in relation to each other or collectively; therefore, it has a temperature of 0[K].

Hypothetically, it may happen if the massive black hole originates from a molecular cloud without any trigger that causes the molecular cloud to spin. Then, after the massive black hole creation, its core does not spin and move. At this stage, the temperature of this black hole's core is 0[K]. However, extremely quickly, the uncertainty-related Energy appearing within the core causes core movement, raising the core temperature above 0[K]. The mantle always contains moving Matter attracted to the core and, therefore, always has a temperature greater than 0[K].

Figure 1 Temperatures within spinning and static-non-spinning massive black holes

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The figure components are not on the same scale.

6. Conclusions

All massive black holes have a core at Dachs density in a non-zero volume.

A massive black hole's core dimensions are substantially smaller than the black hole's total dimensions.

We can prove the existence of a structure of massive black holes by accurately measuring their radius and α .

Possibly, only still, non-rotating massive black holes have 0[K] at their core right after their creation (This is probably a purely hypothetical state.) All other massive black holes' cores and mantles have inner temperatures higher than absolute zero.

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